

Dissociation of PbBr^+ in Aqueous Solutions and Related Thermodynamic Quantities

A. K. PRASAD and B. PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 9 July 1980, revised 20 November 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

The dissociation constant K of $\text{PbBr}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Pb}^{2+} + \text{Br}^-$ has been determined from 5° to 35° at 10° intervals from e.m.f. of the cells of the type

where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone. Assuming B_1 in $\log \gamma_1 = -\frac{AZ_1^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + B_1 \mu$ to be additive and independent of ionic atmosphere, when $\mu < 0.1$, the thermodynamic dissociation constant K of PbBr^+ has been calculated. The value of ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° have also been calculated.

NANCOLLAS¹ from conductance measurement, determined the dissociation constant of PbBr^+ at 25° and 35° . The values obtained are 3.36×10^{-2} and 2.87×10^{-2} respectively.

Biggs, Parton and Robinson² determined the dissociation constant of PbBr^+ spectrophotometrically at 25° . The value obtained is 1.7×10^{-2} . It was decided to determine the dissociation constant of PbBr^+ from 5° to 35° at 10° interval by e.m.f. method.

A cell of the type :

where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone, was employed for this study. In such cell hydrolysis of lead bromide as well as formation of PbOH^+ and its polymers³ if any, would be negligible on account of the presence of hydrogen ions in significant amount.

Experimental

A stock solution of hydrobromic acid (G.R., E. Merck) was prepared by diluting the concentrated acid with double distilled water. The strength of stock solution determined volumetrically⁴ (Borax method) and gravimetrically⁵ (Silver-bromide method) agreed with each other.

Lead bromide was prepared⁶ in the laboratory as it was not available in the market. For this a solution of 39.30 g of KBr (A.R.) in 825 ml of water was added dropwise to a vigorously stirred solution of 54.65 g (equivalent to KBr) of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (A.R.) in 825 ml of water previously acidified with HNO_3

(A.R.) and heated to 60° . The lead bromide so obtained was recrystallised twice from hot water containing four drops of hydrobromic acid (G.R., E. Merck). It was then dried at 120° .

The experimental solutions were prepared by delivering the required amount of hydrobromic acid through a calibrated burette into a weighed 500 ml measuring flask. To this solid lead bromide was added. It was then dissolved by adding double distilled water. When it dissolved completely the volume of the solution in the measuring flask was made upto the mark after it attained the room temperature. The measuring flask was weighed again. Buoyancy correction was made and the concentration in molality of HBr and PbBr_2 were calculated. It may be noted that at different temperatures different solutions were prepared.

The experimental solutions were deoxygenated by passing pure nitrogen gas through water, presaturator and then through experimental solution.

Silver-silver bromide electrode was prepared by thermal electrolytic process as recommended by Harned and Douglas⁷ except for the fact that the platinum spiral was coated with a well washed silver oxide paste whereas Harned and Douglas firstly plated the platinum helix with silver and then coated it with silver oxide. Analytical grade (Renal, Budapest) quinhydrone was recrystallised and dried following the method of Harned and Wright⁸. The electrode vessel, bridges were similar to those used by Prasad and coworkers⁹. The cells were set up in the same way as done by Sinha and Prasad¹⁰. Measurements were made with a Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer. Duplicate experiments performed in each case generally agreed within 0.10 mV. In few cases at 35° differences went up to 0.20 mV.

TABLE I

Mixture of HBr and PbBr ₂		E in abs. volt.	m _{Pb²⁺} × 10 ³	m _{Br⁻} × 10 ³	m _{PbBr⁺} × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³
m ₁ × 10 ³	m ₂ × 10 ³					
<i>Temperature—5°</i>						
2.256	4.510	0.37240	2.870	9.686	1.640	12.506
2.510	5.022	0.37700	3.039	10.579	1.988	13.690
3.016	6.018	0.38509	3.475	12.509	2.548	15.984
3.517	7.031	0.39176	3.789	14.337	3.242	18.126
4.010	8.029	0.39742	4.052	16.091	3.977	20.148
4.516	9.031	0.40267	4.418	17.965	4.613	22.883
5.021	10.041	0.40727	4.686	19.748	5.355	24.484
<i>Temperature—15°</i>						
2.255	4.526	0.36058	3.928	10.109	1.198	13.487
2.508	5.024	0.36540	3.595	11.127	1.429	14.722
2.998	6.018	0.37344	4.029	13.045	1.989	17.078
3.502	7.025	0.38060	4.579	15.106	2.446	19.685
4.010	8.031	0.38660	4.934	16.975	3.097	21.909
4.515	9.032	0.39180	5.209	18.756	3.823	23.965
5.023	10.041	0.39662	5.595	20.659	4.446	26.254
<i>Temperature—25°</i>						
2.254	4.518	0.34824	3.959	10.126	1.154	13.485
2.507	5.019	0.35328	3.648	11.174	1.371	14.822
3.018	6.011	0.36188	4.135	13.159	1.876	17.294
3.506	7.010	0.36918	4.754	15.270	2.256	20.024
4.005	8.017	0.37505	4.927	16.949	3.090	21.895
4.512	9.030	0.38066	5.374	18.916	3.656	24.290
5.014	10.029	0.38554	5.714	20.757	4.315	26.470
<i>Temperature—35°</i>						
2.527	4.523	0.39991	3.179	10.229	1.344	13.408
2.992	6.022	0.34993	3.850	12.864	2.172	16.714
3.497	7.037	0.35740	4.232	14.766	2.805	18.998
4.022	7.530	0.36316	4.525	16.077	3.005	20.602
4.510	9.036	0.36968	4.999	18.544	4.037	23.542
5.015	10.047	0.37471	5.318	20.375	4.734	25.688

The recorded e.m.f. values are the mean of the duplicate cells. Experimental and other significant data are given in Table 1.

Stoichiometric molalities in mole Kg⁻¹ are denoted by m₁ in case of HBr and m₂ in case of PbBr₂.

Discussion

Leaving out charges on the ions, the e.m.f. of the cells of the type :

is given by

$$E = E^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln m_H m_{Br} \gamma_H \gamma_{Br}$$

Therefore,

$$\log m_H m_{Br} = \frac{(E - E^0)F}{2.30259 RT} + \frac{2A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - B\mu \quad \dots (1)$$

where $B = (B_H + B_{Br})$

In equation(1) E⁰ is the standard potential of the cell i.e., E⁰_{cell} = E⁰_{Q.H.} - E⁰_{Ag/AgBr, Br⁻...} (Stockholm convention) ... (2)

The value of E⁰ of quinhydrone has been used as recommended by Bates¹¹ (taken from Ives¹² book) and value of E⁰ of Ag/AgBr, Br⁻ was taken as the mean value of the E⁰ of Ag/AgBr, Br⁻ determined by Sinha and Prasad¹⁰, Harned, Keston and Donelson¹³ and Hetzer, Robinson and Bates¹⁴. The calculated values of E⁰ (abs. volt) of cell (C₁) at various temperatures are given below :

t°C	5	15	25	35
E ⁰	0.63480	0.63146	0.62859	0.62644

The values of A on molality scale are taken from the work of Manov, Bates, Hamer and Acree¹⁵. The value of B in equation (1) was calculated by the author from cell (C₂) ;

9. S. NATH, S. ADITYA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 683.
10. H. K. SINHA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 901.
11. R. G. BATES, "Electrometric pH Determination", Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 175.
12. D. J. G. IVES and G. J. JANZ, "Reference Electrode", Theory and Practice, Academic Press, New York and London, 1961, p. 313.
13. H. S. HARNED, A. S. KESTON and G. J. DONELSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 989.
14. H. B. HETZER, R. A. ROBINSON and R. G. BATES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 1423.
15. G. G. MANOV, R. G. BATES, W. J. HAMER and S. F. ACREE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1765.
16. B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 488.